

Comparison of natural and synthetic ways of carbon capture – Merits & Demerits

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Abstract

The usage of energy is increasing day by day and increase in use of fossil fuels leading to excessive CO₂ emissions in to the atmosphere. This in turn is increasing the global warming effects day by day and escalating the fears of a global catastrophe. To control the current scenario, we need to quickly find measures to control the CO₂ emissions. This paper highlights the various carbon capture methods like Amines, Metal Organic Frameworks and compares them with the carbon capture solutions available in the nature. In this review we will give basic understanding of different processes both natural and artificial methods for carbon dioxide capture. We will also be discussing the recent advancements as well as merits and demerits.

Keywords: Mangroves, MEA, Metal organic frameworks, Carbon capture and sequestration, Energy, Amine, Chemical scrubbing.

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1. Introduction

Every day every hour the world is evolving fast, technologically as well as economically. Therefore increasing the demand of energy day by day. But as we know everything we eat (processed on) things we smell and everything is made up of energy and made from energy. “Energy” this term plays one of the most crucial and very strategic tasks in the events around the globe. Every geopolitical decision rotates around the term energy. About 80% of energy we use is generated from fossil fuels, where the IEO2017 states that the energy consumption rises from 575 quadrillion British thermal units to 736 quadrillion British thermal units with 40% increase [1]. Even in 2040 it is estimated that fossil fuels will account for 77% of total energy usage. So there may not be huge change in usage of fossil fuels for energy purposes. Since 1970, CO₂ emissions have increased nearly about 90% percentage of previous values. Emissions from vehicles and industries account about 78% of the total greenhouse gas emissions increase from 1970 to 2011. Agriculture, deforestation, and other land-use changes will be the second largest contributors [3].

Table 1: Global Carbon Emissions sector wise.

Source of Emissions	%
Electricity and Heat production	25
Agriculture and other land usage	24
Industry (Chemical, Mineral, Metallurgical)	21
Transportation	14
Buildings others	10

Source: [IPCC, 2014] [3].

As per reports from British petroleum, the earth has nearly 1.688 trillion barrels of crude which will last for 53.3 years at current rate of production [7]. Hence carbon sequestration is the term we will hear more and more in coming years. In this paper we will discuss the some of the various methods that are used for carbon capture and also give brief introduction about natural process and artificial process used for carbon capture [3-6].

Figure 1. Global Carbon Emissions (1900-2014).

Source: [18]

2. Natural ways of carbon capture

There are different ways the nature captures CO₂ like ocean capture of carbon dioxide, trees capturing CO₂ and the Mangroves. Nature itself has a cycle of carbon capture in which it absorbs CO₂ and uses it for indirect benefit of the living beings through the process of photosynthesis. The carbon cycle is the circulation and transformation of carbon between living things and the environment. Carbon is an element, something that cannot be broken down into a simpler substance. Other examples of elements are oxygen, nitrogen, calcium, iron, and hydrogen. Carbon compounds are present in both biological and non-biological things. Hence carbon is an omnipresent material. Carbon compounds can exist as solids (such as diamonds or coal), liquids, or gases. Carbon is often referred to as the "god particle for life" because living things are based on carbon and carbon compounds.

Mangroves are forests that grow in the tropics and on coast lines. Mangroves are most carbon rich forests having an carbon dioxide capture capability of 1023 mg/hectare [8]. Mangroves account only for 1% capture of carbon dioxide in total carbon but account about 14% to 20% in tidal regions. Sequestration, generally by growing more mangroves we can have more blue carbon which is defined as capturing

carbon dioxide in aquatic systems. Mangroves look like normal forests but the carbon dioxide intake is very much high when compared to other forests [8].

2.1 Oceans as CO₂ intake and sequestration

Oceans acts as sinks for global carbon dioxide releases and this has been increasing constantly and the studies show how much of CO₂ is into oceans has been started in 1960's [10, 11]. Ocean uptake of carbon dioxide is more prone to climate change and it is very fragile point between 1980-2005. Ocean uptake was about 37+7% [12]. Generally here due to high pressures and low temperatures the CO₂ will be in liquid state so there will be no problem for other measures. The ocean has very high potential of storing CO₂ and it can store carbon dioxide for up to thousands of years [13].

3. Synthetic ways of carbon capture

3.1 Metal Organic Frameworks

Metal Organic Frameworks (MOF's) are kind of structures which have organic frameworks or structure which are joined at nodes or endpoints with inorganic molecules, and these have very unique properties like high porosity.

Figure 2. Metal Organic Frameworks

Source: Authors.

The adsorptive capacity is a critical parameter for consideration when evaluating Metal Organic Frameworks for CO₂ capture. The gravimetric CO₂ uptake, (which refers to the quantity of CO₂ adsorbed within a unit mass of the material) explains the mass of the MOF's required to form the adsorbent bed. Meanwhile, the volumetric capacity refers to how densely the CO₂ can be stored within the material.

Both parameters also have an important role in determining the heating efficiency of the MOF's, which directly impacts the energy penalty required for material regeneration and desorption of the captured CO₂ [12]. Controlling the heating efficiency and volumetric capacity and adsorptive capacity plays a major role in deciding the cost and efficiency of MOF's. The enthalpy of adsorption of CO₂ is a critical parameter that has a significant influence over the performance of a given material for CO₂ capture applications. This in turn plays a crucial role in determining the adsorptive selectivity and the energy required to release the CO₂ molecules during regeneration. Precise control of the binding strength of MOF's is essential to lower the energy requirements of the capture process.

Specifically, the use of a material that binds CO₂ too strongly would increase the regeneration cost owing to the large quantity of energy required in order to break the framework of CO₂ interactions [12]. In CO₂ capture applications, a high selectivity for CO₂ over the other components of the gas mixture is essential. This selectivity can originate from two main mechanisms. In size based selectivity (kinetic separation) and metalorganic framework with small pore size. This will permit molecules only up to a certain kinetic diameter to diffuse into the pores, allowing the molecules to be separated based on size.

3.2 Zeolites

Zeolites are kind of material which have pores (or) holes (< 2nm), these are aluminosilicate materials. These are one of the physical adsorbents methods used other than MOF'S. Generally zeolites are deployed at pressures greater than 4 bars. The main disadvantage, even though having high surface area and higher CO₂ capacity, the efficiency of zeolites decreases due to the presence of moist air in the flue gases mixtures. Due to this reason the regeneration temperature is very high and may reach up to 500°C which is having huge energy penalty on the power plant [15]. Now the research is being focused towards ZIF's (Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks) which are the class of MOF'S where transition metal atoms are connected to the organic molecule called imidazolate (C₃H₃N₂)⁻. The interesting point to note is the process may be anything like Alkanolamines or

amine grafted silica's (chemical adsorption) the common organic term used is amine groups only, because of their affinity towards CO₂. The ZIF'S have high thermal stability and chemical stability these are identical to zeolites. Some of the ZIF'S have very high affinity towards CO₂. One liter of ZIF-69 can store about 83 liters of CO₂ in them [20].

3.3 Chemical absorption (Alkanolamine based absorption)

Generally there are two process called chemical absorption and adsorption for capturing of CO₂ from the flue gases in power plants. One of the processes in chemical absorption is Alkanolamine based absorption. Alkanolamines are widely used as absorbents for CO₂ (amines are derivatives of ammonia where the each hydrogen atom is substituted by the functional group). Major Alkanolamines used are MEA (Mono Ethanol Amine) and DEA (Di Ethanol Amine). The primary amine has the highest reactivity towards the CO₂. Along with the amines generally they use Piperazine (PZ) which acts as a CO₂ capture promoter, PZ forms carbamate rapidly. The reaction of Alkanolamines with the CO₂ is as follows [16].

3.4 Ionic Liquid based absorbents

Ionic liquid is a salt in liquid state. They are generally called as tunable solvents (or) designer solvents (or) "Solvents of Future". They properties like low vapour pressure, non-toxicity, good thermal stability, making it one of the favorable materials for CO₂ capture. We can use ionic liquids in both physical and chemical absorption [16]. Generally for using of Ionic liquids in chemical absorption we have to have an amine functional group in the ionic liquid. Such Ionic liquids are called Task Specific Ionic liquids (TSIL) [17]. They are also known as 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate, also represented as BMIM-PF₆ is one the proposed Ionic liquids for CO₂ capture. The main drawback of using TSIL as material for CO₂ is it has higher viscosity

which makes the regeneration energy higher and finally increasing the cost. Hence blend of Alkanolamines and TSIL has been proposed and are being researched.

3.5 CO₂ capture by adsorption

Adsorption is the process of adhesion (or) sticking of atoms (or) molecules, from gas (or) liquid onto a surface. Here there will be creation of thin film of adsorbate on the surface of the adsorbent. Generally there are certain factors by which we can decide whether the material is suitable for CO₂ capture.

- I. Low cost of raw material used for development of adsorbents.
- II. Fast reaction kinetics.
- III. Higher CO₂ adsorptive capacity.
- IV. Selectivity of CO₂ in combination of different gases.
- V. Stability (Chemical and Thermal)

The above 5 rules can be defined as a standard to check whether the material is suitable for CO₂. There are two types of adsorption namely physical adsorption and chemical. Physical adsorption involves the use of activated carbon where the large amount of carbon is made into powdered form to increase the total surface area. This will aid chemical reactions and as well as capture of different gases. These methods are used because of cheap availability of raw materials and thermal stability. However they lack in high CO₂ adsorptive capacity, and selective CO₂ capture. To increase the CO₂ capture more and to increase the surface area, current research is more focusing towards using of combination of different materials like single walled carbon nanotube, Graphene, Granular Activated Carbons (GAC) with the activated carbon materials. The order of carbon adsorption is high in CNT moderate in modified zeolites and comparatively less in GAC [18].

3.6 Algae based carbon dioxide capture

The cost of actualizing algae-based CO₂ capture systems will be the real main impetus behind changes, and for algae to be valuable in this specific situation. They should be cost aggressive with generally regular, non-biological types of carbon

capture. The expenses of customary CCS are about \$30-50 for every T of CO₂ captured, however it isn't totally clear if the regular strategies are feasible, particularly from innovative and societal points of view.

Algae-based CO₂ capture (and halfway sequestration) costs considerably higher than traditional CCS, however this procedure is more supportable as it likewise delivers items that can be adapted. Algae based CO₂ capture may even present a gainful business suggestion in future as the cost of oil continues rising.

There is growing concern that microalgae are among the most productive biological systems for generating biomass and capturing carbon. Micro-algae's ability to transport bicarbonate into cells makes them well suited to capture carbon. Carbon dioxide or bicarbonate capturing efficiencies as high as 90%. The scale of microalgae production facilities necessary to capture CO₂ emissions from stationary point sources such as power stations and cement kilns is also manageable; thus, microalgae can potentially be exploited for CO₂ capture and sequestration. [19]

4. Conclusion

In this paper we have presented some of the prominent methods that are used for carbon capture process. In this paper these are just an introduction to how does the process happens. There are several different processes being developed ranging from chemical to biological way and other different ways. This paper acts as a foothold for us in this field and acts as a beacon of light for further research. Mainly our research is focused on gas separation in different phases in different temperatures and mainly we focus on ambient air capture and Bio-mimicry of Carbon capture.

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